

η -Separation Axioms in Topological Spaces

¹Hamant Kumar and ²M. C. Sharma

Department of Mathematics

¹Government Degree College, Bilaspur-Rampur, 244921, U. P. (India)

²N. R. E. C. College, Khurja-Bulandshahr, 203131, U. P. (India)

Abstract. The aim of this paper is to introduce and study some new types of separation axioms such as η - T_0 , η - T_1 , η - T_2 , η - R_0 and η - R_1 axioms in topological spaces by using η -open set. The relationships among η - T_0 , η - T_1 , η - T_2 and some other separation axioms are investigated.

Keywords: η -open sets; η -continuous and η -irresolute functions; η - T_k ($k = 0, 1, 2$) and η - R_k ($k = 0, 1$) spaces.

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1. Introduction

In 1965, Njastad [8] introduced the notion of α -open sets. In 1975, Maheswari and Prasad [3] used semi-open sets to introduce the concepts of semi- T_0 , semi- T_1 and semi- T_2 spaces. In 1980, Maheswari and Thakur [4] introduced the concept of α - T_2 space. In 1993, Maki et al. [6] introduced the concept of α - T_0 and α - T_0 spaces. In 2019, Mohammed and Abdullah [7] introduced and investigated the notion of ii-open sets. In 2019, Subbulakshmi et al. [9] introduced and studied the concept of η -open sets. Recently, Kumar [1] used ii-open sets to introduce the concepts of ii- T_0 , ii- T_1 and ii- T_2 separation axioms in topological spaces.

2. Preliminaries

Throughout this paper, spaces (X, \mathfrak{T}) , (Y, τ) , and (Z, η) (or simply X , Y and Z) always mean topological spaces on which no separation axioms are assumed unless explicitly stated. Let A be a subset of a space X . For a subset A of X , $\text{Cl}(A)$ and $\text{Int}(A)$ represents the closure of A and Interior of A respectively.

Definition 2.1. A subset A of a topological space (X, \mathfrak{T}) is said to be

- (i) **semi-open** [2] if $A \subset \text{Cl}(\text{Int}(A))$;
- (ii) **α -open** [8] if $A \subset \text{Int}(\text{Cl}(\text{Int}(A)))$;
- (iii) **η -open** [9] if $A \subset \text{In}(\text{Cl}(\text{Int}(A))) \cup \text{Cl}(\text{Int}(A))$.
- (iii) **η -closed** [9] if $A \supset \text{Cl}(\text{Int}(\text{Cl}(A))) \cup \text{Int}(\text{Cl}(A))$.
- (iv) **ii-open** [7] set if there exists an open set $G \in \mathfrak{T}$, such that

- (a) $G \neq \phi, X$
- (b) $A \subset \text{Cl}(A \cap G)$
- (c) $\text{Int}(A) = G$.

The complement of the semi-open (resp. α -open, η -open, ii-open) set is called semi-closed (resp. α -closed, η -closed, ii-closed). We denote the family of all η -open (resp. η -closed) sets of a topological space by η - $O(X)$ (resp. η - $C(X)$). The η -closure of a subset A of X , is the intersection of all η -closed sets containing A in X and is denoted by η - $\text{Cl}(A)$. The η -interior of a subset A of X is the union of all η -open sets contained in A and is denoted by η - $\text{Int}(A)$.

Remark 2.2. For a subset of a space, we have following implications:

$$\begin{array}{ccccccc} \text{open} & \rightarrow & \alpha\text{-open} & \rightarrow & \text{semi-open} & \rightarrow & \eta\text{-open} \\ & & & & \downarrow & & \\ & & & & \text{ii-open} & & \end{array}$$

Where none of the implications is reversible as can be seen from the following examples:

Example 2.3. Let $X = \{a, b, c\}$ and $\mathfrak{T} = \{\phi, \{a\}, \{b\}, \{a, b\}, X\}$. Then

- (1) α -open sets in (X, \mathfrak{T}) are $\phi, \{a\}, \{b\}, \{a, b\}, X$.
- (2) semi-open sets in (X, \mathfrak{T}) are $\phi, \{a\}, \{b\}, \{a, b\}, \{b, c\}, X$.
- (3) ii-open sets in (X, \mathfrak{T}) are $\phi, \{a\}, \{b\}, \{a, b\}, \{a, c\}, \{b, c\}, X$.
- (4) η -open sets in (X, \mathfrak{T}) are $\phi, \{a\}, \{b\}, \{a, b\}, \{a, c\}, \{b, c\}, X$.

Example 2.4. Let $X = \{a, b, c, d\}$ and $\mathfrak{T} = \{\phi, \{a\}, \{b\}, \{a, b\}, \{a, b, c\}, X\}$. Then

- (1) α -open sets in (X, \mathfrak{T}) are $\phi, \{a\}, \{b\}, \{a, b\}, \{a, b, c\}, \{a, b, d\}, X$.
- (2) semi-open sets in (X, \mathfrak{T}) are $\phi, \{a\}, \{b\}, \{a, b\}, \{a, c\}, \{a, d\}, \{b, c\}, \{b, d\}, \{a, b, c\}, \{a, b, d\}, \{a, c, d\}, \{b, c, d\}, X$.
- (3) η -open sets in (X, \mathfrak{T}) are $\phi, \{a\}, \{b\}, \{a, b\}, \{a, c\}, \{a, d\}, \{b, c\}, \{b, d\}, \{a, b, c\}, \{a, b, d\}, \{a, c, d\}, \{b, c, d\}, X$.
- (4) η -open sets in (X, \mathfrak{T}) are $\phi, \{a\}, \{b\}, \{a, b\}, \{a, c\}, \{a, d\}, \{b, c\}, \{b, d\}, \{a, b, c\}, \{a, b, d\}, \{a, c, d\}, \{b, c, d\}, X$.

Definition 2.5. A space X is said to be:

- (i) **ii-T₀ [1]** if for each pair of distinct points x and y in X , there exists an α -open set G containing x but not y or an α -open set H containing y but not x .
- (ii) **ii-T₁ [1]** if for each pair of distinct points x, y in X , there exist an α -open set G containing x but not y and an α -open set H containing y but not x .
- (iii) **ii-T₂ [1]** if for each pair of distinct points x, y of X , there exist two disjoint α -open sets U and V containing x and y respectively.

Definition 2.6. A space X is said to be:

- (i) **α -T₀ [6]** if for each pair of distinct points x and y in X , there exists an α -open set G containing x but not y or an α -open set H containing y but not x .
- (ii) **α -T₁ [6]** if for each pair of distinct points x, y in X , there exist an α -open set G containing x but not y and an α -open set H containing y but not x .
- (iii) **α -T₂ [4]** if for each pair of distinct points x, y of X , there exist two disjoint α -open sets U and V containing x and y respectively.

Definition 2.7. A space X is said to be:

- (i) **semi-T₀ [3]** if for each pair of distinct points x and y in X , there exists a semi-open set G containing x but not y or a semi-open set H containing y but not x .
- (ii) **semi-T₁ [3]** if for each pair of distinct points x, y in X , there exist a semi-open set G containing x but not y and a semi-open set H containing y but not x .
- (iii) **semi-T₂ [3]** if for each pair of distinct points x, y of X , there exist two disjoint semi-open sets U and V containing x and y respectively.

Definition 2.8. Let X and Y be topological spaces. A function $f : X \rightarrow Y$ is said to be **η -continuous [10]** if the inverse image of every open set in Y is η -open in X .

Definition 2.9. Let X and Y be topological spaces. A function $f : X \rightarrow Y$ is said to be **η -closed** if the image of every closed set in X is η -closed in Y .

Definition 2.10. Let X and Y be topological spaces. A function $f : X \rightarrow Y$ is said to be **η -irresolute** if the inverse image of every η -closed set in Y is η -closed in X .

Definition 2.11. Let X be a topological space. A subset $N \subset X$ is called an **η -neighbourhood [9]** (briefly **η -nhd**) of a point $x \in X$ if there exists an η -open set G such that $x \in G \subset N$.

3. η -T₀ Spaces

In this section, we define η -T₀ space and study some of their properties via some other weaker forms of open sets.

Definition 3.1. A topological space (X, \mathfrak{T}) is said to be **η -T₀** if for each pair of distinct points x, y in X , there exists an η -open set U such that either $x \in U$ and $y \notin U$ or $x \notin U$ and $y \in U$.

Theorem 3.2. (i) Every semi-T₀ space is η -T₀.

- (i) Every semi-T₀ space is η -T₀.
- (ii) Every α -T₀ space is η -T₀.

Proof. (i) Let X be a semi-T₀ space. Let x and y be any two distinct points in X . Since X is semi-T₀, there exists a semi-open set U such that $x \in U$ and $y \notin U$ or $y \in U$ and $x \notin U$. Since every semi-open set is η -open, so U is an η -open set such that $x \in U$ and $y \notin U$ or $y \in U$ and $x \notin U$. Thus X is η -T₀.

(ii) Since every α -open set is semi-open and so, by (i), every α -T₀ space is η -T₀.

Theorem 3.3. Every topological space is η -T₀.

Proof. Since every open set is η -open and so, every T₀ space is η -T₀.

Theorem 3.4. A topological space (X, \mathfrak{T}) is η - T_0 if and only if for each pair of distinct points x, y of X , $\eta\text{-Cl}(\{x\}) \neq \eta\text{-Cl}(\{y\})$.

Proof. Necessity. Let (X, \mathfrak{T}) be an η - T_0 space and x, y be any two distinct points of X . There exists an η -open set U containing x or y , say x but not y . Then $X - U$ is an η -closed set which does not contain x but contains y . Since $\eta\text{-bCl}(\{y\})$ is the smallest η -closed set containing y , $\eta\text{-Cl}(\{y\}) \subset X - U$ and therefore $x \notin \eta\text{-Cl}(\{y\})$. Consequently $\eta\text{-Cl}(\{x\}) \neq \eta\text{-Cl}(\{y\})$.

Sufficiency. Suppose that $x, y \in X$, $x \neq y$ and $\eta\text{-Cl}(\{x\}) \neq \eta\text{-Cl}(\{y\})$. Let z be a point of X such that $z \in \eta\text{-Cl}(\{x\})$ but $z \notin \eta\text{-Cl}(\{y\})$. We claim that $x \notin \eta\text{-Cl}(\{y\})$. For, if $x \in \eta\text{-Cl}(\{y\})$ then $\eta\text{-Cl}(\{x\}) \subset \eta\text{-Cl}(\{y\})$. This contradicts the fact that $z \notin \eta\text{-Cl}(\{y\})$. Consequently x belongs to the η -open set $X - \eta\text{-Cl}(\{y\})$ to which y does not belong.

Theorem 3.5. Every subspace of an η - T_0 space is η - T_0 .

Proof. Let (Y, τ) be a subspace of a topological space (X, \mathfrak{T}) , where τ is the relative topology of \mathfrak{T} on Y . Let x, y be two distinct points of Y . As $Y \subset X$, x and y are also distinct points of X and there exists an η -open set G such that $x \in G$ but $y \notin G$, since X is η - T_0 . Then $G \cap Y$ is an η -open set in (Y, τ) which contains x but does not contain y . Hence (Y, τ) is an η - T_0 space.

4. η - T_1 Spaces

In this section, we define η - T_1 space and study some of their properties via some other weaker forms of open sets.

Definition 4.1. A topological space (X, \mathfrak{T}) is said to be η - T_1 if for each pair of distinct points x, y in X , there exist two η -open sets U and V such that $x \in U$ but $y \notin U$ and $y \in V$ but $x \notin V$.

Theorem 4.2. (i) Every semi- T_1 space is η - T_1 .

(ii) Every α - T_1 space is η - T_1 .

Proof. (i). Suppose X is a semi- T_1 space. Let x and y be two distinct points in X . Since X is semi- T_1 , there exist two semi-open sets U and V such that $x \in U$ but $y \notin U$ and $y \in V$ but $x \notin V$. Since we know that every semi-open set is η -open, so U and V are η -open sets such that $x \in U$ but $y \notin U$ and $y \in V$ but $x \notin V$. Hence X is η - T_1 .

(ii). Since every α -open set is semi-open and so, every α - T_1 space is η - T_1 .

Theorem 4.3. Let $f : X \rightarrow Y$ be an η -irresolute, injective map. If Y is η - T_1 , then X is η - T_1 .

Proof. Assume that Y is η - T_1 . Let $x, y \in X$ with $x \neq y$. Then there exists a pair of η -open sets U, V of Y such that $f(x) \in U$, $f(y) \in V$ and $f(x) \notin V$, $f(y) \notin U$. Then $x \in f^{-1}(U)$, $y \notin f^{-1}(U)$ and $y \in f^{-1}(V)$, $x \notin f^{-1}(V)$. Since f is η -irresolute, X is η - T_1 .

Theorem 4.4. A topological space (X, \mathfrak{T}) is η - T_1 if and only if the singletons are η -closed sets.

Proof. Let (X, \mathfrak{T}) be η - T_1 and x be any point of X . Suppose $y \in X - \{x\}$, then $x \neq y$ and so there exists an η -open set U such that $y \in U$ but $x \notin U$. Consequently $y \in U \subset X - \{x\}$, that is $X - \{x\} = \cup \{U : y \in X - \{x\}\}$ which is η -open.

Conversely, suppose $\{p\}$ is η -closed for every $p \in X$. Let $x, y \in X$ with $x \neq y$. Now $x \neq y$ implies $y \in X - \{x\}$. Hence $X - \{x\}$ is an η -open set contains y but not x . Similarly $X - \{y\}$ is an η -open set contains x but not y . Accordingly, X is an η - T_1 space.

Theorem 4.5. Let $f : X \rightarrow Y$ be bijective.

(i) If f is η -continuous and (Y, \mathfrak{T}_2) is T_1 , then (X, \mathfrak{T}_1) is η - T_1 .

(ii) If f is η -open and (X, \mathfrak{T}_1) is η - T_1 , then (Y, \mathfrak{T}_2) is η - T_1 .

Proof. Let $f : (X, \mathfrak{T}_1) \rightarrow (Y, \mathfrak{T}_2)$ be bijective.

(i) Suppose $f : (X, \mathfrak{T}_1) \rightarrow (Y, \mathfrak{T}_2)$ is η -continuous and (Y, \mathfrak{T}_2) is T_1 . Let $x_1, x_2 \in X$ with $x_1 \neq x_2$. Since f is bijective, $y_1 = f(x_1) \neq f(x_2) = y_2$ for some $y_1, y_2 \in Y$. Since (Y, \mathfrak{T}_2) is T_1 , there exist open sets G and H such that $y_1 \in G$ but $y_2 \notin G$ and $y_2 \in H$ but $y_1 \notin H$. Since f is bijective, $x_1 = f^{-1}(y_1) \in f^{-1}(G)$ but $x_2 = f^{-1}(y_2) \notin f^{-1}(G)$ and $x_2 = f^{-1}(y_2) \in f^{-1}(H)$ but $x_1 = f^{-1}(y_1) \notin f^{-1}(H)$. Since f is η -continuous, $f^{-1}(G)$ and $f^{-1}(H)$ are η -open sets in (X, \mathfrak{T}_1) . It follows that (X, \mathfrak{T}_1) is η - T_1 . This proves (i).

(ii) Suppose f is η -open and (X, \mathfrak{T}_1) is η - T_1 . Let $y_1 \neq y_2 \in Y$. Since f is bijective, there exist x_1, x_2 in X , such that $y_1 = f(x_1)$ and $f(x_2) = y_2$ with $x_1 \neq x_2$. Since (X, \mathfrak{T}_1) is η - T_1 , there exist η -open sets G and H in X such that $x_1 \in G$ but $x_2 \notin G$ and $x_2 \in H$ but $x_1 \notin H$. Since f is η -open, $f(G)$ and $f(H)$ are η -open in Y such that $y_1 = f(x_1) \in f(G)$ and $y_2 = f(x_2) \in f(H)$. Again since f is bijective, $y_2 = f(x_2) \notin f(G)$ and $y_1 = f(x_1) \notin f(H)$. Thus (Y, \mathfrak{T}_2) is η - T_1 . This proves (ii).

Definition 4.6. A topological space (X, \mathfrak{T}) is said to be η -symmetric if for x and y in X , $x \in \eta\text{-Cl}(\{y\})$ implies $y \in \eta\text{-Cl}(\{x\})$.

Theorem 4.7. If (X, \mathfrak{T}) is a topological space, then the following are equivalent:

(i) (X, \mathfrak{T}) is an η -symmetric space.

(ii) $\{x\}$ is η -closed, for each $x \in X$.

Proof. (i) \Rightarrow (ii). Assume that $\{x\} \subset U \in \eta\text{-O}(X)$, but $\eta\text{-Cl}(\{x\}) \not\subset U$. Then $\eta\text{-Cl}(\{x\}) \cap (X - U) \neq \phi$. Now, we take $y \in \eta\text{-Cl}(\{x\}) \cap (X - U)$, then by hypothesis $x \in \eta\text{-Cl}(\{y\}) \subset X - U$ and $x \notin U$, which is a contradiction. Therefore $\{x\}$ is η -closed, for each $x \in X$.

(ii) \Rightarrow (i). Assume that $x \in \eta\text{-Cl}(\{y\})$, but $y \notin \eta\text{-Cl}(\{x\})$. Then $\{y\} \subset X - \eta\text{-Cl}(\{x\})$ and hence $\eta\text{-Cl}(\{y\}) \subset X - \eta\text{-Cl}(\{x\})$. Therefore $x \in X - \eta\text{-Cl}(\{x\})$, which is a contradiction and hence $y \in \eta\text{-Cl}(\{x\})$.

Corollary 4.8. If a topological space (X, \mathfrak{T}) is an $\eta\text{-T}_1$ space, then it is η -symmetric.

Proof. In an $\eta\text{-T}_1$ space, every singleton is η -closed (**Theorem 4.4**) and therefore is by **Theorem 4.7**, (X, \mathfrak{T}) is η -symmetric.

Corollary 4.9. If a topological space (X, \mathfrak{T}) is η -symmetric and $\eta\text{-T}_0$, then (X, \mathfrak{T}) is $\eta\text{-T}_1$.

Proof. Let $x \neq y$ and as (X, \mathfrak{T}) is $\eta\text{-T}_0$, we may assume that $x \in U \subset X - \{y\}$ for some $U \in \eta\text{-O}(X)$. Then $x \notin \eta\text{-Cl}(\{y\})$ and hence $y \notin \eta\text{-Cl}(\{x\})$. There exists an η -open set V such that $y \in V \subset X - \{x\}$ and thus (X, \mathfrak{T}) is an $\eta\text{-T}_1$ space.

5. $\eta\text{-T}_2$ Spaces

In this section, we introduce $\eta\text{-T}_2$ space and investigate some of their basic properties via some other weaker forms of open sets.

Definition 5.1. A space X is said to be $\eta\text{-T}_2$ if for every pair of distinct points x and y in X , there exist disjoint η -open sets U and V of X containing x and y respectively.

Remark 5.2. For a space, we have following implications:

Where none of the implications are reversible as can be seen from the following examples.

Example 5.3. Consider the space (X, \mathfrak{T}) , where $X = \{a, b, c\}$ and $\mathfrak{T} = \{\phi, \{a\}, \{b\}, \{a, b\}, X\}$. Here η -open sets are $\{\phi, \{a\}, \{b\}, \{a, b\}, \{a, c\}, \{b, c\}, X\}$. Since for the distinct points a and b , there exist disjoint η -open sets $U = \{a\}$ and $V = \{b, c\}$ such that $a \in \{a\}$ and $b \in \{b, c\}$. Hence (X, \mathfrak{T}) is $\eta\text{-T}_2$ -space as well as ii- T_2 -space. But it is not $\alpha\text{-T}_2$ -space.

Example 5.4. Consider the space (X, \mathfrak{T}) , where $X = \{a, b, c, d\}$ and $\mathfrak{T} = \{\phi, \{a\}, \{b\}, \{a, b\}, \{a, b, c\}, X\}$. Here η -open sets are $\{\phi, \{a\}, \{b\}, \{a, b\}, \{a, c\}, \{a, d\}, \{b, c\}, \{b, d\}, \{a, b, c\}, \{a, b, d\}, \{a, c, d\}, \{b, c, d\}, X\}$. Since for the distinct points a and b , there exist disjoint η -open sets $U = \{a\}$ and $V = \{b, c\}$ such that $a \in \{a\}$ and $b \in \{b, c\}$. Hence (X, \mathfrak{T}) is $\eta\text{-T}_2$ -space as well as ii- T_2 -space. But it is not $\alpha\text{-T}_2$ -space.

Example 5.5. Consider the space (X, \mathfrak{T}) , where $X = \{a, b, c, d\}$ and $\mathfrak{T} = \{\phi, \{a\}, \{b\}, \{a, b\}, X\}$. Then (X, \mathfrak{T}) is semi- T_2 as well as $\eta\text{-T}_2$. But it is not $\alpha\text{-T}_2$.

Theorem 5.6. (i) Every semi- T_2 space is $\eta\text{-T}_2$.

(ii) Every $\alpha\text{-T}_2$ space is $\eta\text{-T}_2$.

Proof. (i) Let X be a semi- T_2 space. Let x and y be two distinct points in X . Since X is semi- T_2 space, there exist disjoint semi-open sets U and V such that $x \in U$ and $y \in V$. Since every semi-open set is η -open, so U and V are disjoint η -open sets such that $x \in U$ and $y \in V$. Hence X is $\eta\text{-T}_2$.

(ii) Suppose X is α - T_2 space. Let x and y be two distinct points in X . Since X is α - T_2 , there exist disjoint α -open sets U and V such that $x \in U$ and $y \in V$. Since every α -open set is semi-open, so U and V are disjoint η -open sets such that $x \in U$ and $y \in V$. Hence X is η - T_2 .

Theorem 5.7. Every η - T_2 space is η - T_1 .

Proof. Let X be an η - T_2 space. Let x and y be two distinct points of X . Since X is η - T_2 , there exist disjoint η -open sets U and V such that $x \in U$ and $y \in V$. Since U and V are disjoint, so $x \in U$ but $y \notin U$ and $y \in V$ but $x \notin V$. Hence X is η - T_1 .

Theorem 5.8. For a topological space X , the following are equivalent:

- (i) X is an η - T_2 space.
- (ii) Let $x \in X$. Then for each $x \neq y$, there exists an η -open set U such that $x \in U$ and $y \notin \eta\text{-Cl}(U)$.
- (iii) For each $x \in X$, $\bigcap \{\eta\text{-Cl}(U) : U \in \eta\text{-O}(X) \text{ and } x \in U\} = \{x\}$.

Proof. (i) \Rightarrow (ii). Suppose X is an η - T_2 space. Then for each $x \neq y$, there exist disjoint η -open sets U and V such that $x \in U$ and $y \in V$. Since V is η -open, V^c is η -closed and $U \subset V^c$. This implies that $\eta\text{-Cl}(U) \subset V^c$. Since $y \notin V^c$, $y \notin \eta\text{-Cl}(U)$.

(ii) \Rightarrow (iii). If $y \neq x$, then there exists an η -open set U such that $x \in U$ and $y \notin \eta\text{-Cl}(U)$. Therefore $y \notin \bigcap \{\eta\text{-Cl}(U) : U \in \eta\text{-O}(X) \text{ and } x \in U\}$. Therefore $\bigcap \{\eta\text{-Cl}(U) : U \in \eta\text{-O}(X) \text{ and } x \in U\} = \{x\}$. This proves (iii).

(iii) \Rightarrow (i). Let $y \neq x$ in X . Then $y \notin \{x\} = \bigcap \{\eta\text{-Cl}(U) : U \in \eta\text{-O}(X) \text{ and } x \in U\}$. This implies that there exists an η -open set U such that $x \in U$ and $y \notin \eta\text{-Cl}(U)$. Let $V = (\eta\text{-Cl}(U))^c$. Then V is η -open and $y \in V$. Now $U \cap V = U \cap (\eta\text{-Cl}(U))^c \subset U \cap (U)^c = \phi$. Therefore, X is η - T_2 space.

Theorem 5.9. Let $f : X \rightarrow Y$ be a bijection.

- (i) If f is η -open and X is T_2 , then Y is η - T_2 .
- (ii) If f is η -continuous and Y is T_2 , then X is η - T_2 .

Proof. Let $f : X \rightarrow Y$ be a bijection.

(i) Suppose F is η -open and X is T_2 . Let $y_1 \neq y_2 \in Y$. Since f is a bijection. There exist x_1, x_2 in X such that $f(x_1) = y_1$ and $f(x_2) = y_2$ with $x_1 \neq x_2$. Since X is T_2 , there exist disjoint open sets U and V in X such that $x_1 \in U$ and $x_2 \in V$. Since f is η -open, $f(U)$ and $f(V)$ are η -open in Y such that $y_1 = f(x_1) \in f(U)$ and $y_2 = f(x_2) \in f(V)$. Again since f is a bijection, $f(U)$ and $f(V)$ are disjoint in Y . Thus Y is η - T_2 .

(ii) Suppose $f : X \rightarrow Y$ is η -continuous and Y is T_2 . Let $x_1, x_2 \in X$ with $x_1 \neq x_2$. Let $y_1 = f(x_1)$ and $y_2 = f(x_2)$. Since f is one-one, $y_1 \neq y_2$. Since Y is T_2 , there exist disjoint open sets U and V containing y_1 and y_2 respectively. Since f is η -continuous bijective, $f^{-1}(U)$ and $f^{-1}(V)$ are disjoint η -open sets containing x_1 and x_2 respectively. Thus X is η - T_2 .

Theorem 5.10. A topological space (X, \mathfrak{T}) is η - T_2 if and only if the intersection of all η -closed, η -neighbourhoods of each point of the space is reduced to that point.

Proof. Let (X, \mathfrak{T}) be η - T_2 and $x \in X$. Then for each $y \neq x$ in X , there exist disjoint η -open sets U and V such that $x \in U$, $y \in V$. Now $U \cap V = \phi$ implies $x \in U \subset V^c$. Therefore V^c is an η -neighbourhood of x . Since V is η -open, V^c is η -closed and η -neighbourhood of x to which y does not belong. That is there is an η -closed, η -neighbourhoods of x which does not contain y . So we get the intersection of all η -closed, η -neighbourhood of x is $\{x\}$.

Conversely, let $x, y \in X$ such that $x \neq y$ in X . Then by assumption, there exist an η -closed, η -neighbourhood V of x such that $y \notin V$. Now there exists an η -open set U such that $x \in U \subset V$. Thus U and V^c are disjoint η -open sets containing x and y respectively. Thus (X, \mathfrak{T}) is η - T_2 .

Theorem 5.11. If $f : X \rightarrow Y$ be bijective, η -irresolute map and X is η - T_2 , then (X, \mathfrak{T}_2) is η - T_2 .

Proof. Suppose $f : (X, \mathfrak{T}_1) \rightarrow (Y, \mathfrak{T}_2)$ is bijective. f is η -irresolute, and (Y, \mathfrak{T}_2) is η - T_2 . Let $x_1, x_2 \in X$ with $x_1 \neq x_2$. Since f is bijective, $y_1 = f(x_1) \neq f(x_2) = y_2$ for some $y_1, y_2 \in Y$. Since (Y, \mathfrak{T}_2) is η - T_2 , there exist disjoint η -open sets G and H such that $y_1 \in G$ and $y_2 \in H$. Again since f is bijective, $x_1 = f^{-1}(y_1) \in f^{-1}(G)$ and $x_2 = f^{-1}(y_2) \in f^{-1}(H)$. Since f is η -irresolute, $f^{-1}(G)$ and $f^{-1}(H)$ are η -open sets in (X, \mathfrak{T}_1) . Also f is bijective, $G \cap H = \phi$ implies that $f^{-1}(G) \cap f^{-1}(H) = f^{-1}(G \cap H) = f^{-1}(\phi) = \phi$. It follows that (X, \mathfrak{T}_2) is η - T_2 .

6. η - R_k Space ($k = 0, 1$)

In this section, new classes of topological spaces called, η - R_0 and η - R_1 spaces are introduced.

Definition 6.1. A topological space (X, \mathfrak{T}) is said to be η - R_0 if U is an η -open set and $x \in U$ then $\eta\text{-Cl}(\{x\}) \subset U$.

Theorem 6.2. For a topological space (X, \mathfrak{T}) the following properties are equivalent:

- (i) (X, \mathfrak{T}) is η - R_0 .
- (ii) For any $F \in \eta\text{-C}(X)$, $x \notin F$ implies $F \subset U$ and $x \notin U$ for some $U \in \eta\text{-O}(X)$.
- (iii) For any $F \in \eta\text{-C}(X)$, $x \notin F$ implies $F \cap \eta\text{-Cl}(\{x\}) = \phi$.

(iv) For any distinct points x and y of X , either $\eta\text{-Cl}(\{x\}) = \eta\text{-Cl}(\{y\})$ or $\eta\text{-Cl}(\{x\}) \cap \eta\text{-Cl}(\{y\}) = \phi$.

Proof. (i) \Rightarrow (ii). Let $F \in \eta\text{-C}(X)$ and $x \notin F$. Then by (i), $\eta\text{-Cl}(\{x\}) \subset X - F$. Set $U = X - \eta\text{-Cl}(\{x\})$, then U is an η -open set such that $F \subset U$ and $x \notin U$.

(ii) \Rightarrow (iii). Let $F \in \eta\text{-C}(X)$ and $x \notin F$. There exists $U \in \eta\text{-O}(X)$ such that $F \subset U$ and $x \notin U$. Since $U \in \eta\text{-O}(X)$, $U \cap \eta\text{-Cl}(\{x\}) = \phi$ and $F \cap \eta\text{-Cl}(\{x\}) = \phi$.

(iii) \Rightarrow (iv). Suppose that $\eta\text{-Cl}(\{x\}) \neq \eta\text{-Cl}(\{y\})$ for distinct points $x, y \in X$. There exists $z \in \eta\text{-Cl}(\{x\})$ such that $z \notin \eta\text{-Cl}(\{y\})$ (or $z \in \eta\text{-Cl}(\{y\})$ such that $z \notin \eta\text{-Cl}(\{x\})$). There exists $V \in \eta\text{-O}(X)$ such that $y \notin V$ and $z \in V$; hence $x \in V$. Therefore, we have $x \notin \eta\text{-Cl}(\{y\})$. By (iii), we obtain $\eta\text{-Cl}(\{x\}) \cap \eta\text{-Cl}(\{y\}) = \phi$.

(iv) \Rightarrow (i). Let $V \in \eta\text{-O}(X)$ and $x \in V$. For each $y \notin V$, $x \neq y$ and $x \notin \eta\text{-Cl}(\{y\})$. This shows that $\eta\text{-Cl}(\{x\}) \neq \eta\text{-Cl}(\{y\})$. By (iv), $\eta\text{-Cl}(\{x\}) \cap \eta\text{-Cl}(\{y\}) = \phi$ for each $y \in X - V$ and hence $\eta\text{-Cl}(\{x\}) \cap (\cup_{y \in X - V} \eta\text{-Cl}(\{y\})) = \phi$. On other hand, since $V \in \eta\text{-O}(X)$ and $y \in X - V$, we have $\eta\text{-Cl}(\{y\}) \subset X - V$ and hence $X - V = \cup_{y \in X - V} \eta\text{-Cl}(\{y\})$. Therefore, we obtain $(X - V) \cap \eta\text{-Cl}(\{x\}) = \phi$ and $\eta\text{-Cl}(\{x\}) \subset V$. This shows that (X, \mathfrak{T}) is an $\eta\text{-R}_0$ space.

Theorem 6.3. If a topological space (X, \mathfrak{T}) is $\eta\text{-T}_0$ and an $\eta\text{-R}_0$ space then it is $\eta\text{-T}_1$.

Proof. Let x and y be any distinct points of X . Since X is $\eta\text{-T}_0$, there exists an η -open set U such that $x \in U$ and $y \notin U$. As $x \in U$ implies that $\eta\text{-Cl}(\{x\}) \subset U$. Since $y \notin U$, so $y \notin \eta\text{-Cl}(\{x\})$. Hence $y \in V = X - \eta\text{-Cl}(\{x\})$ and it is clear that $x \notin V$. Hence it follows that there exist η -open sets U and V containing x and y respectively, such that $y \notin U$ and $x \notin V$. This implies that X is $\eta\text{-T}_1$.

Theorem 6.4. For a topological space (X, \mathfrak{T}) the following properties are equivalent:

- (i) (X, \mathfrak{T}) is $\eta\text{-R}_0$.
- (ii) $x \in \eta\text{-Cl}(\{y\})$ if and only if $y \in \eta\text{-Cl}(\{x\})$, for any points x and y in X .

Proof. (i) \Rightarrow (ii). Assume that X is $\eta\text{-R}_0$. Let $x \in \eta\text{-Cl}(\{y\})$ and V be any η -open set such that $y \in V$. Now, by hypothesis, $x \in V$. Therefore, every η -open set which contain y contains x also. Hence $y \in \eta\text{-Cl}(\{x\})$.

(ii) \Rightarrow (i). Let U be an η -open set and $x \in U$. If $y \notin U$, then $x \notin \eta\text{-Cl}(\{y\})$ and hence $y \notin \eta\text{-Cl}(\{x\})$. This implies that $\eta\text{-Cl}(\{x\}) \subset U$. Hence (X, \mathfrak{T}) is $\eta\text{-R}_0$.

From **Definition 4.6** and **Theorem 6.4**, the notions of η -symmetric and $\eta\text{-R}_0$ are equivalent.

Definition 6.5. Let A be a subset of a topological space (X, \mathfrak{T}) . The η -kernel of A , denoted by $\eta\text{-ker}(A)$ is defined to be the set

$$\eta\text{-ker}(A) = \cap \{U \in \eta\text{-O}(X) : A \subset U\}.$$

Theorem 6.6. Let (X, \mathfrak{T}) be a topological space and $x \in X$. Then $y \in \eta\text{-ker}(\{x\})$ if and only if $x \in \eta\text{-Cl}(\{y\})$.

Proof. Suppose that $y \notin \eta\text{-ker}(\{x\})$. Then there exists an η -open set V containing x such that $y \notin V$. Therefore, we have $x \notin \eta\text{-Cl}(\{y\})$. The proof of the converse case can be done similarly.

Theorem 6.7. Let (X, \mathfrak{T}) be a topological space and A be a subset of X . Then, $\eta\text{-ker}(A) = \{x \in X : \eta\text{-Cl}(\{x\}) \cap A \neq \phi\}$.

Proof. Let $x \in \eta\text{-ker}(A)$ and suppose $\eta\text{-Cl}(\{x\}) \cap A = \phi$. Hence $x \notin X - \eta\text{-Cl}(\{x\})$ which is an η -open set containing A . This is impossible, since $x \in \eta\text{-ker}(A)$. Consequently, $\eta\text{-Cl}(\{x\}) \cap A \neq \phi$. Next, let $x \in X$ such that $\eta\text{-Cl}(\{x\}) \cap A \neq \phi$ and suppose that $x \notin \eta\text{-ker}(A)$. Then, there exists an η -open set V containing A and $x \notin V$. Let $y \in \eta\text{-Cl}(\{x\}) \cap A$. Hence, V is an η -neighbourhood of y which does not contain x . By this contradiction $x \in \eta\text{-ker}(A)$ and the claim.

Definition 6.8. A subset A of a topological space X is called an η -difference set (briefly, $\eta\text{-D-set}$) if there are $U, V \in \eta\text{-O}(X)$ such that $U \neq X$ and $A = U - V$.

Theorem 6.9. The following properties hold for the subsets A, B of a topological space (X, \mathfrak{T}) :

- (i) $A \subset \eta\text{-ker}(A)$.
- (ii) $A \subset B$ implies that $\eta\text{-ker}(A) \subset \eta\text{-ker}(B)$.
- (iii) If A is η -open in (X, \mathfrak{T}) , then $A = \eta\text{-ker}(A)$.
- (iv) $\eta\text{-ker}(\eta\text{-ker}(A)) = \eta\text{-ker}(A)$.

Proof. (i), (ii) and (iii) are immediate consequences of **Definition 6.5**. To prove (iv), first observe that by (i) and (ii), we have $\eta\text{-ker}(A) \subset \eta\text{-ker}(\eta\text{-ker}(A))$. If $x \notin \eta\text{-ker}(A)$, then there exists $U \in \eta\text{-O}(X)$ such that $A \subset U$ and $x \notin U$. Hence $\eta\text{-ker}(A) \subset U$, and so we have $x \notin \eta\text{-ker}(\eta\text{-ker}(A))$. Thus $\eta\text{-ker}(\eta\text{-ker}(A)) = \eta\text{-ker}(A)$.

Proposition 6.10. If a singleton $\{x\}$ is an η -D-set of (X, \mathfrak{T}) , then $\eta\text{-ker}(\{x\}) \neq X$.

Proof. Since $\{x\}$ is an η -D-set of (X, \mathfrak{T}) , then there exist two subsets $U_1, U_2 \in \eta\text{-O}(X)$ such that $\{x\} = U_1 - U_2$, $\{x\} \subset U_1$ and $U_1 \neq X$. Thus, we have that $\eta\text{-ker}(\{x\}) \subset U_1 \neq X$ and so $\eta\text{-ker}(\{x\}) \neq X$.

Theorem 6.11. The following statements are equivalent for any points x and y in a topological space (X, \mathfrak{T}) :

- (i) $\eta\text{-ker}(\{x\}) \neq \eta\text{-ker}(\{y\})$.
- (ii) $\eta\text{-Cl}(\{x\}) \neq \eta\text{-Cl}(\{y\})$.

Proof. (i) \Rightarrow (ii). Suppose that $\eta\text{-ker}(\{x\}) \neq \eta\text{-ker}(\{y\})$, then there exists a point z in X such that $z \in \eta\text{-ker}(\{x\})$ and $z \notin \eta\text{-ker}(\{y\})$. From $z \in \eta\text{-ker}(\{x\})$ it follows that $\{x\} \cap \eta\text{-Cl}(\{z\}) \neq \emptyset$ which implies $x \in \eta\text{-Cl}(\{z\})$. By $z \notin \eta\text{-ker}(\{y\})$, we have $\{y\} \cap \eta\text{-Cl}(\{z\}) = \emptyset$. Since $x \in \eta\text{-Cl}(\{z\})$, $\eta\text{-Cl}(\{x\}) \subset \eta\text{-Cl}(\{z\})$ and $\{y\} \cap \eta\text{-Cl}(\{x\}) = \emptyset$. Therefore, it follows that $\eta\text{-Cl}(\{x\}) \neq \eta\text{-Cl}(\{y\})$. Now $\eta\text{-ker}(\{x\}) \neq \eta\text{-ker}(\{y\})$ implies that $\eta\text{-Cl}(\{x\}) \neq \eta\text{-Cl}(\{y\})$.

(ii) \Rightarrow (i). Suppose that $\eta\text{-Cl}(\{x\}) \neq \eta\text{-Cl}(\{y\})$. Then there exists a point z in X such that $z \in \eta\text{-Cl}(\{x\})$ and $z \notin \eta\text{-Cl}(\{y\})$. Then, there exists an η -open set containing z and therefore x but not y , namely, $y \notin \eta\text{-ker}(\{x\})$ and thus $\eta\text{-ker}(\{x\}) \neq \eta\text{-ker}(\{y\})$.

Theorem 6.12. Let (X, \mathfrak{T}) be a topological space. Then $\bigcap \{\eta\text{-Cl}(\{x\}) : x \in X\} = \emptyset$ if and only if $\eta\text{-ker}(\{x\}) \neq X$ for every $x \in X$.

Proof. Necessity. Suppose that $\bigcap \{\eta\text{-Cl}(\{x\}) : x \in X\} = \emptyset$. Assume that there is a point y in X such that $\eta\text{-ker}(\{y\}) = X$. Let x be any point of X . Then $x \in V$ for every η -open set V containing y and hence $y \in \eta\text{-Cl}(\{x\})$ for any $x \in X$. This implies that $y \in \bigcap \{\eta\text{-Cl}(\{x\}) : x \in X\}$. But this is a contradiction.

Sufficiency. Assume that $\eta\text{-ker}(\{x\}) \neq X$ for every $x \in X$. If there exists a point y in X such that $y \in \bigcap \{\eta\text{-Cl}(\{x\}) : x \in X\}$, then every η -open set containing y must contain every point of X . This implies that the space X is the unique η -open set containing y . Hence $\eta\text{-ker}(\{y\}) = X$ which is a contradiction. Therefore, $\bigcap \{\eta\text{-Cl}(\{x\}) : x \in X\} = \emptyset$.

Theorem 6.13. A topological space (X, \mathfrak{T}) is $\eta\text{-R}_0$ if and only if for every x and y in X , $\eta\text{-Cl}(\{x\}) \neq \eta\text{-Cl}(\{y\})$ implies $\eta\text{-Cl}(\{x\}) \cap \eta\text{-Cl}(\{y\}) = \emptyset$.

Proof. Necessity. Suppose that (X, \mathfrak{T}) is $\eta\text{-R}_0$ and $x, y \in X$ such that $\eta\text{-Cl}(\{x\}) \neq \eta\text{-Cl}(\{y\})$. Then, there exists $z \in \eta\text{-Cl}(\{x\})$ such that $z \notin \eta\text{-Cl}(\{y\})$ (or $z \in \eta\text{-Cl}(\{y\})$ such that $z \notin \eta\text{-Cl}(\{x\})$). There exists $V \in \eta\text{-O}(X)$ such that $y \notin V$ and $z \in V$, hence $x \in V$. Therefore, we have $x \notin \eta\text{-Cl}(\{y\})$. Thus $x \in [X - \eta\text{-Cl}(\{y\})] \in \eta\text{-O}(X)$, which implies $\eta\text{-Cl}(\{x\}) \subset [X - \eta\text{-Cl}(\{y\})]$ and $\eta\text{-Cl}(\{x\}) \cap \eta\text{-Cl}(\{y\}) = \emptyset$.

Sufficiency. Let $V \in \eta\text{-O}(X)$ and let $x \in V$. We still show that $\eta\text{-Cl}(\{x\}) \subset V$. Let $y \notin V$, that is $y \in X - V$. Then $x \neq y$ and $x \notin \eta\text{-Cl}(\{y\})$. This shows that $\eta\text{-Cl}(\{x\}) \neq \eta\text{-Cl}(\{y\})$. By assumption, $\eta\text{-Cl}(\{x\}) \cap \eta\text{-Cl}(\{y\}) = \emptyset$. Hence $y \notin \eta\text{-Cl}(\{x\})$ and therefore $\eta\text{-Cl}(\{x\}) \subset V$.

Theorem 6.14. A topological space (X, \mathfrak{T}) is $\eta\text{-R}_0$ if and only if for any points x and y in X , $\eta\text{-ker}(\{x\}) \neq \eta\text{-ker}(\{y\})$ implies $\eta\text{-ker}(\{x\}) \cap \eta\text{-ker}(\{y\}) = \emptyset$.

Proof. Suppose that (X, \mathfrak{T}) is an $\eta\text{-R}_0$ space. Thus by **Theorem 6.11**, for any points x and y in X if $\eta\text{-ker}(\{x\}) \neq \eta\text{-ker}(\{y\})$ then $\eta\text{-Cl}(\{x\}) \neq \eta\text{-Cl}(\{y\})$. Now we prove that $\eta\text{-ker}(\{x\}) \cap \eta\text{-ker}(\{y\}) = \emptyset$. Assume that $z \in \eta\text{-ker}(\{x\}) \cap \eta\text{-ker}(\{y\})$. By $z \in \eta\text{-ker}(\{x\})$ and **Theorem 6.6**, it follows that $x \in \eta\text{-Cl}(\{z\})$. Since $x \in \eta\text{-Cl}(\{x\})$, by **Theorem 6.2**, $\eta\text{-Cl}(\{x\}) = \eta\text{-Cl}(\{z\})$. Similarly, we have $\eta\text{-Cl}(\{y\}) = \eta\text{-Cl}(\{z\}) = \eta\text{-Cl}(\{x\})$. This is a contradiction. Therefore, we have $\eta\text{-ker}(\{x\}) \cap \eta\text{-ker}(\{y\}) = \emptyset$.

Conversely, let (X, \mathfrak{T}) be a topological space such that for any points x and y in X , $\eta\text{-ker}(\{x\}) \neq \eta\text{-ker}(\{y\})$ implies $\eta\text{-ker}(\{x\}) \cap \eta\text{-ker}(\{y\}) = \emptyset$. If $\eta\text{-Cl}(\{x\}) \neq \eta\text{-Cl}(\{y\})$, then by **Theorem 6.11**, $\eta\text{-ker}(\{x\}) \neq \eta\text{-ker}(\{y\})$. Hence, $\eta\text{-ker}(\{x\}) \cap \eta\text{-ker}(\{y\}) = \emptyset$ which implies $\eta\text{-Cl}(\{x\}) \cap \eta\text{-Cl}(\{y\}) = \emptyset$. Because $z \in \eta\text{-Cl}(\{x\})$ implies that $x \in \eta\text{-ker}(\{z\})$ and therefore $\eta\text{-ker}(\{x\}) \cap \eta\text{-ker}(\{z\}) \neq \emptyset$. By hypothesis, we have $\eta\text{-ker}(\{x\}) = \eta\text{-ker}(\{z\})$. Then $z \in \eta\text{-Cl}(\{x\}) \cap \eta\text{-Cl}(\{y\})$ implies that $\eta\text{-ker}(\{x\}) = \eta\text{-ker}(\{z\}) = \eta\text{-ker}(\{y\})$. This is a contradiction. Therefore, $\eta\text{-Cl}(\{x\}) \cap \eta\text{-Cl}(\{y\}) = \emptyset$ and by **Theorem 6.2**, (X, \mathfrak{T}) is an $\eta\text{-R}_0$ space.

Theorem 6.15. For a topological space (X, \mathfrak{T}) the following properties are equivalent:

- (i) (X, \mathfrak{T}) is an $\eta\text{-R}_0$ space.

- (ii) For any non-empty set A and $G \in \eta\text{-O}(X)$ such that $A \cap G \neq \phi$, there exists $F \in \eta\text{-C}(X)$ such that $A \cap F \neq \phi$ and $F \subset G$.
 (iii) For any $G \in \eta\text{-O}(X)$, we have $G = \cup \{F \in \eta\text{-C}(X) : F \subset G\}$.
 (iv) For any $F \in \eta\text{-C}(X)$, we have $F = \cap \{G \in \eta\text{-O}(X) : F \subset G\}$.
 (v) For every $x \in X$, $\eta\text{-Cl}(\{x\}) \subset \eta\text{-ker}(\{x\})$.

Proof. (i) \Rightarrow (ii). Let A be a non-empty subset of X and $G \in \eta\text{-O}(X)$ such that $A \cap G \neq \phi$. There exists $x \in A \cap G$. Since $x \in G \in \eta\text{-O}(X)$, $\eta\text{-Cl}(\{x\}) \subset G$. Set $F = \eta\text{-Cl}(\{x\})$, then $F \in \eta\text{-C}(X)$, $F \subset G$ and $A \cap F \neq \phi$.

(ii) \Rightarrow (iii). Let $G \in \eta\text{-O}(X)$, then $G \supset \cup \{F \in \eta\text{-C}(X) : F \subset G\}$. Let x be any point of G . There exists $F \in \eta\text{-C}(X)$ such that $x \in F$ and $F \subset G$. Therefore, we have $x \in F \subset \cup \{F \in \eta\text{-C}(X) : F \subset G\}$ and hence $G = \cup \{F \in \eta\text{-C}(X) : F \subset G\}$.

(iii) \Rightarrow (iv). Obvious.

(iv) \Rightarrow (v). Let x be any point of X and $y \notin \eta\text{-ker}(\{x\})$. There exists $V \in \eta\text{-O}(X)$ such that $x \in V$ and $y \notin V$, hence $\eta\text{-Cl}(\{y\}) \cap V = \phi$. By (iv), $(\cap \{G \in \eta\text{-O}(X) : \eta\text{-Cl}(\{y\}) \subset G\}) \cap V = \phi$ and there exists $G \in \eta\text{-O}(X)$ such that $x \notin G$ and $\eta\text{-Cl}(\{y\}) \subset G$. Therefore $\eta\text{-Cl}(\{x\}) \cap G = \phi$ and $y \notin \eta\text{-Cl}(\{x\})$. Consequently, we obtain $\eta\text{-Cl}(\{x\}) \subset \eta\text{-ker}(\{x\})$.

(v) \Rightarrow (i). Let $G \in \eta\text{-O}(X)$ and $x \in G$. Let $y \in \eta\text{-ker}(\{x\})$, then $x \in \eta\text{-Cl}(\{y\})$ and $y \in G$. This implies that $\eta\text{-ker}(\{x\}) \subset G$. Therefore, we obtain $x \in \eta\text{-Cl}(\{x\}) \subset \eta\text{-ker}(\{x\}) \subset G$. This shows that (X, \mathfrak{T}) is an $\eta\text{-R}_0$ space.

Corollary 6.16. For a topological space (X, \mathfrak{T}) the following properties are equivalent:

- (i) (X, τ) is an $\eta\text{-R}_0$ space.
 (ii) $\eta\text{-Cl}(\{x\}) = \eta\text{-ker}(\{x\})$ for all $x \in X$.

Proof. (i) \Rightarrow (ii). Suppose that (X, \mathfrak{T}) is an $\eta\text{-R}_0$ space. By **Theorem 6.15**, $\eta\text{-Cl}(\{x\}) \subset \eta\text{-ker}(\{x\})$ for each $x \in X$. Let $y \in \eta\text{-ker}(\{x\})$, then $x \in \eta\text{-Cl}(\{y\})$ and by **Theorem 6.2**, $\eta\text{-Cl}(\{x\}) = \eta\text{-Cl}(\{y\})$. Therefore, $y \in \eta\text{-Cl}(\{x\})$ and hence $\eta\text{-ker}(\{x\}) \subset \eta\text{-Cl}(\{x\})$. This shows that $\eta\text{-Cl}(\{x\}) = \eta\text{-ker}(\{x\})$.

(ii) \Rightarrow (i). Follows from **Theorem 6.15**.

Theorem 6.17. For a topological space (X, \mathfrak{T}) the following properties are equivalent:

- (i) (X, \mathfrak{T}) is an $\eta\text{-R}_0$ space.
 (ii) If F is η -closed, then $F = \eta\text{-ker}(F)$.
 (iii) If F is η -closed and $x \in F$, then $\eta\text{-ker}(\{x\}) \subset F$.
 (iv) If $x \in X$, then $\eta\text{-ker}(\{x\}) \subset \eta\text{-Cl}(\{x\})$.

Proof. (i) \Rightarrow (ii). Let F be an η -closed and $x \notin F$. Thus $(X - F)$ is an η -open set containing x . Since (X, \mathfrak{T}) is $\eta\text{-R}_0$, $\eta\text{-Cl}(\{x\}) \subset (X - F)$. Thus $\eta\text{-Cl}(\{x\}) \cap F = \phi$ and by **Theorem 6.7**, $x \notin \eta\text{-ker}(F)$. Therefore $\eta\text{-ker}(F) = F$.

(ii) \Rightarrow (iii). In general, $A \subset B$ implies $\eta\text{-ker}(A) \subset \eta\text{-ker}(B)$. Therefore, it follows from (ii), that $\eta\text{-ker}(\{x\}) \subset \eta\text{-ker}(F) = F$.

(iii) \Rightarrow (iv). Since $x \in \eta\text{-Cl}(\{x\})$ and $\eta\text{-Cl}(\{x\})$ is η -closed, by (iii), $\eta\text{-ker}(\{x\}) \subset \eta\text{-Cl}(\{x\})$.

(iv) \Rightarrow (i). We show the implication by using **Theorem 6.4**. Let $x \in \eta\text{-Cl}(\{y\})$. Then by **Theorem 6.6**, $y \in \eta\text{-ker}(\{x\})$. Since $x \in \eta\text{-Cl}(\{x\})$ and $\eta\text{-Cl}(\{x\})$ is η -closed, by (iv), we obtain $y \in \eta\text{-ker}(\{x\}) \subset \eta\text{-Cl}(\{x\})$. Therefore $x \in \eta\text{-Cl}(\{y\})$ implies $y \in \eta\text{-Cl}(\{x\})$. The converse is obvious and (X, \mathfrak{T}) is $\eta\text{-R}_0$.

Definition 6.18. A topological space (X, \mathfrak{T}) is said to be $\eta\text{-R}_1$ if for x, y in X with $\eta\text{-Cl}(\{x\}) \neq \eta\text{-Cl}(\{y\})$, there exist disjoint η -open sets U and V such that $\eta\text{-Cl}(\{x\}) \subset U$ and $\eta\text{-Cl}(\{y\}) \subset V$.

Theorem 6.19. A topological space (X, \mathfrak{T}) is $\eta\text{-R}_1$ if it is $\eta\text{-T}_2$.

Proof. Let x and y be any points of X such that $\eta\text{-Cl}(\{x\}) \neq \eta\text{-Cl}(\{y\})$. By **Theorem 5.7**, every $\eta\text{-T}_2$ space is $\eta\text{-T}_1$. Therefore, by **Theorem 4.4**, $\eta\text{-Cl}(\{x\}) = \{x\}$, $\eta\text{-Cl}(\{y\}) = \{y\}$ and hence $\{x\} \neq \{y\}$. Since (X, \mathfrak{T}) is $\eta\text{-T}_2$, there exist disjoint η -open sets U and V such that $\eta\text{-Cl}(\{x\}) = \{x\} \subset U$ and $\eta\text{-Cl}(\{y\}) = \{y\} \subset V$. This shows that (X, \mathfrak{T}) is $\eta\text{-R}_1$.

Theorem 6.20. If a topological space (X, \mathfrak{T}) is η -symmetric, then the following are equivalent:

- (i) (X, \mathfrak{T}) is $\eta\text{-T}_2$.
 (ii) (X, \mathfrak{T}) is $\eta\text{-R}_1$ and $\eta\text{-T}_1$.
 (iii) (X, \mathfrak{T}) is $\eta\text{-R}_1$ and $\eta\text{-T}_0$.

Proof. Straightforward.

Theorem 6.21. For a topological space (X, \mathfrak{T}) the following statements are equivalent:

(i) (X, \mathfrak{T}) is η - R_1 .

(ii) If $x, y \in X$ such that $\eta\text{-Cl}(\{x\}) \neq \eta\text{-Cl}(\{y\})$, then there exist η -closed sets F_1 and F_2 such that $x \in F_1, y \notin F_1, y \in F_2, x \notin F_2$ and $X = F_1 \cup F_2$.

Proof. Obvious.

Theorem 6.22. If (X, \mathfrak{T}) is η - R_1 , then (X, \mathfrak{T}) is η - R_0 .

Proof. Let U be an η -open set such that $x \in U$. If $y \notin U$, since $x \notin \eta\text{-Cl}(\{y\})$, we have $\eta\text{-Cl}(\{x\}) \neq \eta\text{-Cl}(\{y\})$. So, there exists an η -open set V such that $\eta\text{-Cl}(\{y\}) \subset V$ and $x \notin V$, which implies $y \notin \eta\text{-Cl}(\{x\})$. Hence $\eta\text{-Cl}(\{x\}) \subset U$. Therefore, (X, \mathfrak{T}) is η - R_0 .

Corollary 6.23. A topological space (X, \mathfrak{T}) is η - R_1 if and only if for $x, y \in X, \eta\text{-ker}(\{x\}) \neq \eta\text{-ker}(\{y\})$, there exist disjoint η -open sets U and V such that $\eta\text{-Cl}(\{x\}) \subset U$ and $\eta\text{-Cl}(\{y\}) \subset V$.

Proof. Follows from **Theorem 6.11**.

Theorem 6.24. A topological space (X, \mathfrak{T}) is η - R_1 if and only if $x \in X - \eta\text{-Cl}(\{y\})$ implies that x and y have disjoint η -open neighbourhoods.

Proof. Necessity. Let $x \in X - \eta\text{-Cl}(\{y\})$. Then $\eta\text{-Cl}(\{x\}) \neq \eta\text{-Cl}(\{y\})$, so, x and y have disjoint η -open neighbourhoods.

Sufficiency. First, we show that (X, \mathfrak{T}) is η - R_0 . Let U be an η -open set and $x \in U$. Suppose that $y \notin U$. Then, $\eta\text{-Cl}(\{y\}) \cap U = \emptyset$ and $x \notin \eta\text{-Cl}(\{y\})$. There exist η -open sets U_x and U_y such that $x \in U_x, y \in U_y$ and $U_x \cap U_y = \emptyset$. Hence, $\eta\text{-Cl}(\{x\}) \subset \eta\text{-Cl}(U_x)$ and $\eta\text{-Cl}(\{x\}) \cap U_y \subset \eta\text{-Cl}(U_x) \cap U_y = \emptyset$. Therefore, $y \notin \eta\text{-Cl}(\{x\})$. Consequently, $\eta\text{-Cl}(\{x\}) \subset U$ and (X, \mathfrak{T}) is η - R_0 . Next, we show that (X, \mathfrak{T}) is η - R_1 . Suppose that $\eta\text{-Cl}(\{x\}) \neq \eta\text{-Cl}(\{y\})$. Then, we can assume that there exists $z \in \eta\text{-Cl}(\{x\})$ such that $z \notin \eta\text{-Cl}(\{y\})$. There exist η -open sets V_z and V_y such that $z \in V_z, y \in V_y$ and $V_z \cap V_y = \emptyset$. Since $z \in \eta\text{-Cl}(\{x\})$, $x \in V_z$. Since (X, \mathfrak{T}) is η - R_0 , we obtain $\eta\text{-Cl}(\{x\}) \subset V_z, \eta\text{-Cl}(\{y\}) \subset V_y$ and $V_z \cap V_y = \emptyset$. This shows that (X, \mathfrak{T}) is η - R_1 .

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